

GEOGRAPHICAL REGIONAL SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF THE ORIGIN OF VARIOUS FORMS OF ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION IN THE FARMING POPULATION

Mamasoliev N.S.¹

Nishonova N.A.²

Umurzakova R.Z.³

¹⁻²⁻³Andijan State Medical Institute, Uzbekistan

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The aim of the study was to study the geographical regional specific aspects of the origin of mild (EAG), moderate (O'OAG) and severe forms of arterial hypertension (OAG) in the farming population (FAP).

Research material and methods. A representative group of 1069 farmers population (236 -18-30-year-olds, 31-49-year-olds - 606, 50-69-year-olds - 194, > 70-year-olds - 33) was comprehensively examined in a simultaneous epidemiological study. Mild, moderate and severe forms of arterial hypertension were diagnosed and assessed using epidemiological, clinical, biochemical and instrumental examination methods.

Obtained results and conclusions. > in FAP aged 18-70, EAG - 5.6% (in men - 6.6% and women - 4.6%; $p < 0.05$), O'OAG - 6.2% (in men - 6.2% and in women - 6.3%; $p = 0.374$) and OAG - 0.7% (-1.0% in men and 0.4% in women; $p < 0.05$) are recorded with the frequency of dispersion.

Mild AG is identified with an age-dependent increase of up to 2.6 times, confirmed with a lower frequency of 3.7 and 6.1% in men compared to women under the age of 30 and after the age of 70 { RR = 1.45; Cl - low = 1.0, Cl - up = 2.1; $\chi^2 = 4.38$; $p = 0.036$ }.

O'OAG varies according to age with prevalence rates of 3.4% (18-30 years old), 6.1% (31-49 years old), 7.7% (50-69 years old) and > 70 years old - 16.4% . { RR = 0.98; Cl - low = 0.69; Cl - up = 1.39; $\chi^2 = 0.01$; $p = 0.911$. Depending on age, OAG is confirmed in the examined OAP - 0.5 -0.5% (18-30 years old), 0.5 (0.5%) and > 70 years old - 0.0%. Specific features of the geographic region are of preventive and therapeutic importance.